

Eligibility Criteria

Criterion	Keep	Discard
Population	PD, MS, Hip Fracture, COPD, heart failure Mixed populations IF a sub-analysis was conducted	Animal Studies All other human disease areas Mixed populations with no sub-analysis
Study Aim	Studies an included Gait and Walking Parameter according to one of our research questions	Studies with no GaWP and/or which do not address a RQ
Study Design	Case-control, cross sectional, longitudinal, cohort, controlled trials, protocols (RQ4 only)	Case study, case series Systematic review (or any review)
Technology	Basically any (sensors, stopwatch, speed gaits, instrumented walkways, video, optometric systems, etc.) Specific clinical tests regardless of technology use (see below)	Pedometers
Setting	Any (home, clinical, lab-based)	NA

Minimum Dataset

RQ1	5 patients per study arm included in the final analysis	RQ3	Age, sex, and disease severity are included as covariates At least 20 recorded events of an outcome of interest
RQ2	5 patients included in the final analysis	RQ4	5 patients per study arm included in final analysis

Gait and Walking Parameters

Spatial Parameters

Step length (mean, variability, asym.)
Stride length (mean, variability)
Step width (mean, variability)

Temporal Parameters

Cadence (mean, variability)
Step time (mean, variability, asymmetry)
Stride time (mean, variability)
Stance time (mean, variability, asymmetry)
Swing time (mean, variability, asymmetry)
Single support time (mean, variability, asym.)
Double support time (mean, variability)

Spatiotemporal Parameters

Gait speed (mean, variability)
Stride speed (mean, variability)

Volume of Walking

Walking time
Step count (excluding pedometer)
Number, length, duration of walking bouts

Included Walking Conditions

Keep:

- Gait analysis or measurement of any included gait parameters
- Dual-task walking, if testing scenario is included
- Some clinical tests, even no technology was used:
 - 4, 5, 10, 30, 50, etc. meter walk tests (or other short distance) – INCLUDE as gait speed
 - Timed 25 Foot Walk (T25FW) - INCLUDE as gait speed
 - 2 Minute Walk Test – INCLUDE as gait speed

Conditionally Keep:

- Timed Up & Go: ONLY INCLUDE instrumented TUG w/ GaWPs measured during walk
- Treadmill Walking:
 - Fixed-Speed Treadmill: INCLUDE any GaWP EXCEPT gait speed
 - Self-Adjusting Speed Treadmill: INCLUDE any GaWP
- 6Minute WT, 12Minute WT, 400m WT, (or other long walking tests):
 - Non-Instrumented Test: EXCLUDE
 - Instrumented test: INCLUDE any GaWP EXCEPT gait speed

Keep if normal gait may have been analyzed at baseline or if walking condition was used as intervention (generally keep to be conservative):

- Tandem walking or other abnormal walking patterns
- Walking in time to cues (e.g., beats, music, beeping, etc.)
- Purposefully altering gait (e.g., instructions to concentrate on lifting toes)

Research Questions

RQ1: Comparison of GAWPs between a Mobilise-D population and healthy controls

RQ2: Association between a GaWP and a clinical measurement at a single timepoint

RQ3: Prognostic value: Longitudinal association between a GaWP and a clinical measurement or outcome over time

RQ4: Use of GaWPs as endpoints in controlled interventional studies

Population Terms

	Keep	Discard
PD	Parkinson('s) disease, Parkinsonism, idiopathic Parkinson's disease	Atypical parkinsonian syndromes, drug-induced parkinsonism, vascular parkinsonism, progressive supranuclear palsy, multiple system atrophy, corticobasal syndrome, dementia with lewy bodies
MS	Multiple Sclerosis, relapsing-remitting, primary progressive, secondary progressive MS	
PFF	Hip, femoral, intracapsular (subcapital and transcervical), extracapsular (trochanteric, intertrochanteric, pertrochanteric and subtrochanteric) fractures	Non-fracture-related hip arthroplasty or hip replacement
COPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease Chronic obstructive lung disease Chronic respiratory disease (>age of 65)	Pulmonary hypertension, Studies only including asthma patients

- *If the population is mixed, the study must conduct a sub-analysis of one of our populations to be included. If this is unclear from the abstract, be conservative and include.*
- *If you are unsure about the population and the paper meets all other inclusion criteria, include the paper and the disease-specific team will make the determination.*

FAQs

What do I do when...

I am not sure whether a measurement or outcome is included in RQ2/3 criteria

- Some determinations may require disease-specific knowledge. Be conservative and keep the paper.

A testing scenario or type of study is not covered by our eligibility criteria

- If something is not covered by eligibility criteria, raise a question to Ashley and others in the group. We may need to clarify an unforeseen situation.

The abstract does not indicate the technology or method used to measure a GaWP/DMO?

- Include the paper IF it mentions measuring an included gait parameter, gait analysis, or included clinical test of gait speed AND IF it meets all of our other inclusion criteria

Something is completely unclear, and I can't tell whether to include?

- Think about the item that is unclear with regard to the other inclusion criteria. How realistic is it that the criterion is met, given the information that you have?
- Be pragmatic, but inclusive. If all else fails, be conservative and keep the paper.